

EPIDEMIOLOGY OF DEGENERATIVE SPINE INJURIES

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The purpose of the study is to study the epidemiology of degenerative spine injuries (DIS) in the population of adolescents and adults living in the conditions of the Fergana Valley.

Test material and methods. A 21-year (2000-2020) retrospective epidemiological study was conducted in Andijan. Its object is the Republican Urgent First Aid Scientific Center of Andijan Filiali departments. the population of the population who underwent a course of treatment in the departments was taken. In the prospective epidemiological-clinical study of 2000-2020, a comprehensive study was conducted with a total of 2994 DIS (1241 were men and 1753 were women).

It is described by age as follows. <20-year-olds - 25 (0.8%), 20-29-year-olds - 382 (12.8%), 30-39-year-olds - 511 (17.1), 40-49-year-olds - 627 (20, 9%), 50-59-year-olds - 721 (24.1%), 60-74-year-olds - 644 (21.5%) and ≥75-year-olds - 84 (2.8%). The first conclusion was made that for 21 years, the number of women, working people, rural population, married people, disabled people, foreign population, 20-29 years old, 60-74 years old and ≥ old people increased with DIS. Urban residents, <20-year-olds, 30-39-year-olds, 40-49-year-olds and 50-59-year-olds, with DIS, have decreased in number.

The study was organized and carried out in accordance with the requirements of epidemiological investigations and using WHO criteria. The study was carried out in 5 stages with the personal participation of a researcher-researcher who was trained and trained in standardized and unified epidemiological investigation methods.

General questionnaire (epidemiological), biochemical, pharmacoepidemiological, clinical, instrumental, special and statistical methods were used. WHO recommendation.

It was diagnosed and evaluated using the risk factors and criteria of DIS [WHO, 2020].

X-ray examinations and MRI were considered the most important in the diagnosis of DIS, in addition to screening and clinical-biochemical results.

A collection of new and reliable special programs was used in the statistical processing of the obtained data. For example, data collection, editing and initial data systematization and visualization were performed on MateBook D14 "Huawei" personal computer with Windows 10 software.

Analyzing the data of the 21st year of epidemiological research showed logically scientific and practically significant results in the population of the valley for the first time in relation to DIS, confirmed the epidemiological conditions that truly represent DIS.

DIS is confirmed with a prevalence of 70.4% in the patient population, with a change from 68.5% to 97.0% over 21 years of monitoring, i.e., with an increase in detection reaching a frequency of 28.5%. It is confirmed in the sedentary population with a prevalence of 69.6% (with a growth rate of 30.3%) and in the immigrant population with a prevalence of 72.7% (a significant difference from the sedentary population by 3.1%).

In the male and female population-69.4% (confirming a 21-year increase of 1.3 times) and 71.1% (showing an increase of 29.2%) are recorded with corresponding prevalence rates.

Such epidemiologic trends of 21 years are expressed in the rural population (confirming the growth of DIS from 54.7% to 70.1%) and in the urban population (confirming the growth rate from 78.8% to 100.0%). It is generally known that over the last two decades, there is a tendency and increase in DIS to be detected at higher frequencies.

The frequency of growth is confirmed by age in the general population, in men and women, in rural and urban populations. In particular, the frequency of this increase in men is 2.3 times and in women 1.3 times, with an increase, in the rural population - 1.4 times, in the urban population - 2.9 times, in the sedentary population - 36.6%, and in the immigrant population - 45, It is observed expressed in a 21-year trend with an age-related increase in frequency of 4%.

Epidemiological, clinical, biochemical and instrumental examination methods were used. The diagnosis was made using generally accepted criteria and the WOMC scale.

Research results and conclusions. According to the 21-year epidemiological description, DIS is confirmed with a high frequency (70.4%) in the inpatient population (ID). The 21-year trend, in this population, is represented by a change from 68.5% to 97.0% and or an increase in DIS up to 28.5% ($\chi^2=2.597$; $S=0.029$; $RR=0.957$; $95\% \text{ CI}=0.910 - 1.008$; $P>0.05$). Detection of prevalence in the resident population - 69.6% and in the migrant population - 72.6%, in the

male population - 69.4% and in the female population - 71.1%, in the rural and urban population - 70.1% and 71.2% DIS with frequency is confirmed. It is worth noting that this disease is detected in high frequency in ID and is represented by an increasing trend in recent years.

